

Magneto-electric Coupling in BaTiO₃/Sr₂CoO₃F heterostructure

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ABSTRACT

By means of first-principles calculations, we study the electronic and magnetic properties of a cobalt oxyhalide¹ Sr₂CoO₃F (SCOF) perovskite in a hybrid heterostructure, combined with BaTiO₃ (BTO) in different polarization states (see Fig 1.). The calculations show that the spin state of Co atom in SCOF changed from High Spin (HS) state to Intermediate Spin (IS) state by introducing ferroelectric state in BTO. The IS state of SCOF system shows the half-metallic nature due to strong p-d σ hybridization². The change in spin state of Co atom controlled by altering the polarization direction. Such changes in spin state results a large magneto-electric coupling constant. Moreover, this change in spin state by applying the polarization opens the possibilities to design and develop new type of future spintronic devices, in particular, storage devices by controlling the magnetism with electric fields.

Fig 1: Atomic structure of of three types BTO-SCOF-BTO [001] multilayer configurations. P1 is Nonpolar system, BTO is paraelectric, P2 and P3 are polar systems, BTO is ferroelectric. The arrows mark the polarization orientation.

References

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